

D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services

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Lead Participant	SZE	Lead Author	László Környei (SZE)
Contributors	ATOS, PSNC, SZE, USTUTT, UNISTRA, ICCS, MTG, FAU	Reviewers	Gwennole Chappron (UNISTRA)
			Angela Rivera Campos (MTG)

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Document Information

List of Contributors	
Name	Partner
László Környei	SZE
Németh Áron Ákos	SZE
Sameer Haroon	USTUTT
Christophe Prud'homme	UNISTRA
Philippe Pinçon	UNISTRA
Luis Torres	MTG
Michael Zikeli	FAU
Bartosz Bosak	PSNC
Jesus Gorroñogoitia Cruz	ATOS
Konstantinos Nikas	ICCS
Zoltán Horváth	SZE

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Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	3 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

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Role	Who (Partner short name)	Approval Date
Deliverable leader	László Környei (SZE)	30/06/2026
Quality manager	Shubham Kavane (FAU)	30/06/2026
Project Coordinator	Marcin Lawenda (PSNC)	30/06/2026

Table of Contents

Document Information	3
Table of Contents	4
List of Tables	6
List of Figures	6
List of Acronyms	7
Executive Summary	9
1 Introduction	10
1.1 Purpose of the document	10
1.2 Relation to other project work	10
1.3 Structure of the document	10
2 Dashboard current release	11
2.1 Improved layout and design	12
2.2 Improved functionality	13
2.3 Improved WFO Integration	14
3 Dashboard services	16
3.1 HiDALGO2 ecosystem	16
3.1.1 Current list of services	17
3.1.2 External services	19
3.2 User and right management	19
3.2.1 Authentication levels	20
3.2.2 User registration and management	21
3.2.3 Onboarding of new users	22

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	4 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

- 4 Pilot integration into the Dashboard.....23
 - 4.1 UAP23
 - 4.1.1 Technical details of integration23
 - 4.1.2 Sequence of user flow25
 - 4.2 UB.....29
 - 4.2.1 Technical details of integration29
 - 4.2.2 Sequence of user flow30
 - 4.3 RES32
 - 4.3.1 Technical details of integration33
 - 4.3.2 Sequence of user flow34
 - 4.4 WF37
 - 4.4.1 Technical details of integration38
 - 4.4.2 Sequence of user flow38
 - 4.5 MTW43
 - 4.5.1 Technical details of integration43
 - 4.5.2 Sequence of user flow44
- 5 Feedback, suggestions and additional requirements.....47
 - 5.1 Questionnaire design47
 - 5.2 Questionnaire results48
 - 5.3 Results analysis57
- 6 Conclusions and Roadmap.....60
 - 6.1 Conclusion60
 - 6.2 Roadmap61
- References62
- Annexes.....63
 - Annex I. Internal feedback on the Dashboard.....63

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	5 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

List of Tables

Table 1: Supporting Services	17
Table 2: Development Services	17
Table 3: Steps of the RES workflow executed in QCG	35
Table 4: Distribution and average of questionnaire results compared to previous average.	57

List of Figures

Figure 1. Overview of the current version of the Dashboard in compact mode	12
Figure 2. The first, fourth and fifth window of the introductory Quick Tour, which walks through the most important elements of the Dashboard	12
Figure 3. Part of the element editor showing the basic information, category, image and description sections	13
Figure 4. Access and settings pane controlling guest access, guest-only access and portal integration	14
Figure 5. Deployment action from the MTW Dashboard entry to the MathSO Portal application catalogue filtered by the mtw tag	15
Figure 6. HiDALGO2 Ecosystem	16
Figure 7. Supporting Services in Dashboard	18
Figure 8. Pilot Code services in the Dashboard	19
Figure 9. Selecting simulation domain for RedSIM within Stockholm city for wind comfort calculations	26
Figure 10. Configuration interface for Xyst within the MathSO portal	27
Figure 11. Configuring emission type within the UAP-FOAM configuration panel of the MathSO portal. No emission, point source, and EMI-file based emission may be selected.	28
Figure 12. Demonstrating the 3D results of a RedSIM simulation within CFDR, opened from the MathSO portal.	28
Figure 13. Accessing UB pilot in HiDALGO2 Dashboard	31
Figure 14. Figure Ktirio WASM Graphical Interface	31
Figure 15. RES Entry in HiDALGO2 Dashboard	34
Figure 16. RES Simulation Parameters (light mode)	35
Figure 17. RES workflow execution progress monitoring (dark mode)	36
Figure 18. RES analysis results (light mode)	37
Figure 19. WF Entry in HiDALGO2 Dashboard	39
Figure 20. WF Input parameters specification form - general settings	40
Figure 21. WF Input parameters specification form - ignition points set-up	41
Figure 22. JSON file generated by the WF GUI during submission.	42
Figure 23. WF workflow execution monitoring in QCG	43
Figure 24. (left) MTW Application Blueprint; (right) HPC Configuration Overview	44
Figure 25. (left) MTW Dashboard Entry; (right) HPC Resource Availability	44
Figure 26. (left) Application Page with MTW Filter for Instance Creation; (right) MTW Instance Configuration	45
Figure 27. Execute Page	45
Figure 28. (left) Execution Graph; (right) Log Inspection	46
Figure 29. Experiments Page	46

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	6 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 30. Distribution of questionnaire answers from partners.	48
Figure 31. Questionnaire results from internal partners evaluating design	49
Figure 32. Questionnaire results from internal partners evaluating layout	50
Figure 33. Questionnaire results from internal partners evaluating functionalities	51
Figure 34. Questionnaire results from internal partners evaluating usability and responsiveness	52
Figure 35. Questionnaire results from internal partners evaluating integration support	54

List of Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
2FA	Two-Factor Authentication
CFDR	Computer Fluid Dynamics Rendering
CKAN	Comprehensive Knowledge Archive Network
Dx.y	Deliverable number y belonging to WP x
EC	European Commission
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HDFS	Hadoop Distributed File System
HPC	High Performance Computing
IAM	Identity and Access Management
IDM	Identity Manager
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
KUB	Ktirio Urban Building
MathSO	Mathematical Simulation and Optimization
MFA	Multi-Factor Authentication
MTW	Material Transport in Water
OIDC	OpenID Connect
QCG	QCG Workflow Orchestrator
RedSIM	Reduced Simulations
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SSO	Single Sign-On
UB	Urban Building
UAP	Urban Air Pilot
UAP-FOAM	OpenFOAM-based UAP framework

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	7 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

WASM	Web Assembly
WF	Wildfires
WFO	Workflow Orchestrator
WP	Work Package

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	8 of 71	
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status:	Final

Executive Summary

Deliverable D2.9 builds on D2.7 and D2.8 and reports the current state of the HiDALGO2 Dashboard as an operational entry point to the project ecosystem. The Dashboard now provides improved layout options, compact and personalized views, onboarding support, catalogue editing, and direct links to workflow execution environments. It gives users a unified interface for accessing pilots, workflow orchestrators, data-management services, visualization tools, documentation, training resources and collaboration services.

The current release strengthens the connection between the Dashboard and the HiDALGO2 workflow infrastructure. Dashboard entries can open the relevant MathSO or QCG applications directly, while authenticated users can also see selected portal-related information, such as recent deployments, active jobs and HPC-system status. The deliverable describes the integration of the main pilots: Urban Air Pollution, Urban Building, Renewable Energy Sources, Wildfire and Material Transport in Water.

D2.9 also describes the current user and rights management approach. Authentication is handled through the HiDALGO2 IDM service based on Keycloak, while the Dashboard uses roles, groups and organization membership to control service visibility and management functions. Public, internal and controlled external access are distinguished, and onboarding remains partly manual because several services require additional permissions or credentials.

The second internal questionnaire confirms that the Dashboard has improved since the previous feedback round. Design, layout, functionality, usability and integration support were all evaluated positively, with no critical ratings. Remaining suggestions focus on practical refinements, including scrolling behavior, responsiveness, clearer service relationships, improved tags, better documentation and debugging support for workflow developers, and evaluation of selected additional services.

Overall, D2.9 shows that the Dashboard and Services are largely complete for internal operational use and mature enough for controlled external scenarios. The remaining roadmap focuses on stabilization and refinement rather than major redesign.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	9 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

The deliverable D2.9 “HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services” is a continuation of deliverables D2.7 and D2.8 of the same name. It elaborates the Dashboard in terms of functionality and details how already delivered and existing backend services and pilot applications are integrated with the HiDALGO2 platform including orchestration, data management, visualization and complimentary services. While the Dashboard will cover expectations of both internal and external stakeholders, at this point only internal stakeholders were considered.

1.2 Relation to other project work

This document – continuing D2.7 and D2.8 – is based on the rationale of integrating services and strategies from deliverables within HiDALGO2, in addition to updated requirements gathered in D2.2 “Requirements Analysis and Scenario Definitions” Additionally, it aligns with D4.2 “Data Management and Coupling Technologies” and provides a platform for both the upcoming D4.8 “Visualization for Global Challenges” and the recently updated D2.6 “Infrastructure Provisioning, Workflow Orchestration and Component Integration.”

1.3 Structure of the document

The document is structured into six main sections. After introduction in Section 1, Section 2 details the current release of the Dashboard focusing on layout, design, functionalities and pilot deployment.

Section 3 details the integration of HiDALGO2 services, starting with currently integrated ones, detailing level of integration. It also discusses user registration and management.

Section 4 details the integration of pilot applications into the Dashboard. This consists of the technical details of the integration itself and the sequence of user flow, and how users will experience pilot execution.

Section 5 reports on the second internal questionnaire conducted with internal stakeholders as described in D2.7. Questionnaire design and results are discussed, including results analysis.

Finally, Section 6 summarizes and concludes this deliverable while giving an outlook about near future objectives to be wrapped up until the end of the project.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	10 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

2 Dashboard current release

The current release of the HiDALGO2 Dashboard provides a unified entry point to the pilots, workflow systems, data and visualization services, documentation, training resources and collaboration tools of the HiDALGO2 ecosystem. Dashboard entries are presented as searchable service cards containing a title, short description, image, category, tags, service provider and one or more actions. Public information and authenticated operational services are presented through the same interface, while access restrictions are applied according to the user session and the metadata of each entry.

The Dashboard supports three presentation modes: list, grid and compact view. The compact view is especially useful for larger catalogues, as it reduces the amount of vertical space required by each service entry while keeping the most important actions directly accessible. Users can search the catalogue and filter it by category, functional tags and service provider. Results can also be sorted by title, provider or category. Category grouping can be displayed as sections or tabs, reducing long scrolling in larger catalogues. The interface is responsive and adapts to mobile phones, tablets, desktop displays and wide screens.

The latest release also introduces personalization for authenticated users. Dashboard entries can be pinned, recently used services can be displayed, and the composition and order of Dashboard sections can be customized. User preferences are stored per account, preventing preferences from being shared between different users of the same browser. Light, dark and system-controlled visual themes are available. An onboarding flow introduces the main navigation and interaction patterns to new users. Figure 1 shows the current version of the Dashboard in compact mode. New visible features include compact service icons, pinned icons and recently used icons. The portal pane on the right-hand side displays recent deployments and the status of pinned HPC sites, giving authenticated users a concise operational overview directly from the Dashboard.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	11 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 1. Overview of the current version of the Dashboard in compact mode

2.1 Improved layout and design

The design and interaction changes in the current release respond to feedback collected through the first user questionnaire and subsequent reviews. The catalogue now uses a clearer category structure, supports smaller card formats and limits content width on large displays. The filter area was reorganized, and the distinction between categories, functional tags and service providers was made more explicit. Service details can be opened without losing the catalogue context, and outbound actions are visually identified as external links.

Figure 2. The first, fourth and fifth window of the introductory Quick Tour, which walks through the most important elements of the Dashboard

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	12 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

The compact view was added to improve overview and reduce scrolling when many services are displayed. This is especially useful for users who already know the available services and want quick access to frequently used Dashboard entries. Together with pinning and recently used services, the compact layout supports faster navigation while keeping the Dashboard readable.

To support new users, the current release includes an introductory Quick Tour. This guided onboarding sequence explains the most important Dashboard areas and interaction patterns, including service cards, actions, personalization and portal-related information. Figure 2 shows selected windows of the Quick Tour.

Figure 3. Part of the element editor showing the basic information, category, image and description sections

2.2 Improved functionality

Navigation was improved by making the HiDALGO2 logo return to the main Dashboard and by adding direct access to the MathSO and QCG portals. Search recognizes the metadata of Dashboard entries; while filtering and sorting update the visible catalogue

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	13 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

immediately. Personalization features allow authenticated users to pin frequently used entries and quickly return to recently used services.

Administrators and authorized organization members can maintain catalogue entries through the Dashboard editor. The editor supports the modification of basic service information, category assignment, images, descriptions, tags, target URLs, access settings and portal-integration metadata. Users with appropriate rights can add new elements and edit existing elements belonging to their organization. Figure 3 shows part of the element editor, including the sections for basic information, category, image and description.

The editor also contains an access and settings pane. This pane controls whether an entry is visible for guest users, restricted to guests only, or connected to portal functionality. Enabling MathSO integration requires a list of application tags, which are later used to open the MathSO Portal with the corresponding application filter applied. Enabling QCG integration requires an application link, which is opened when the user selects the deployment action. Figure 4 shows the access and settings pane.

Figure 4. Access and settings pane controlling guest access, guest-only access and portal integration

2.3 Improved WFO Integration

For authenticated users, the Dashboard is no longer limited to static links. It connects to the MathSO Portal APIs using the user’s Keycloak access token and can display selected Portal information directly on the Dashboard. This includes pinned Portal applications, deployment statistics, active and recent jobs, deployment progress, pinned HPC systems and their usage information. The integration provides a concise

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	14 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

operational overview while keeping detailed application configuration and execution functions in the Portal.

Dashboard entries may also contain MathSO and QCG Portal application metadata. When the user selects the deployment action of such an entry, the Dashboard opens the appropriate portal application catalogue with the relevant filter or application link already applied. This creates a direct transition from pilot discovery in the Dashboard to the corresponding executable application in the workflow orchestrator.

Figure 5 shows this deployment action for the MTW pilot. Activating the MTW deployment icon on the Dashboard opens the list of applications in the MathSO Portal with the **mtw** tag already assigned. This reduces the number of manual steps required from the user and connects the high-level Dashboard description of the pilot with the executable applications available in the workflow system.

Figure 5. Deployment action from the MTW Dashboard entry to the MathSO Portal application catalogue filtered by the mtw tag

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	15 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

3 Dashboard services

3.1 HiDALGO2 ecosystem

The HiDALGO2 Dashboard is the centre of the HiDALGO2 ecosystem. This ecosystem combines a varied set of components from different categories and work packages. This includes Workflow Orchestrators that are used to customise and set up pilot code simulations, supporting web services such as ticketing systems and wikis, as well as internal development services such as code repositories. Figure 6 from deliverable, D2.60 is inserted here for to give an overview of the HiDALGO2 ecosystem.

Figure 6. HiDALGO2 Ecosystem

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	16 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

3.1.1 Current list of services

The HiDALGO2 Dashboard collects and integrates the various services offered by the HiDALGO2 ecosystem. These services are divided into supporting services, as listed in Table 1, and development services, as listed in Table 2.

Table 1: Supporting Services

	Service	Description	Access Status
1	Website	Project Website	Integrated
2	Dashboard	Workflow Orchestrator	Self
3	Keycloak	Identity Management	Implicit
4	Zabbix	Monitoring Solution	N/A
5	AskBot	User Forums	Integrated with Single-Sign-On.
6	Zammad	User Support	Integrated with Single-Sign-On.
7	Wiki	Knowledge Management	Integrated with Single-Sign-On.
8	Open Project	Project Management	Integrated
9	Moodle	Learning Platform	Integrated with Single-Sign-On.
10	HedgeDoc	Collaborative Notes	Integrated with Single-Sign-On.

Table 2: Development Services

	Service	Description	Access Status
1	Altair HPC	In-house HPC System	Through WFOs.
2	Eagle HPC	In-house HPC System	Through WFOs.
3	Prototype	Compute Cluster	Integrated with Single-Sign-On.
4	JupyterHub	Jupyter Notebooks	Integrated with Single-Sign-On.
5	CKAN	Data Catalogue Storage	Integrated with Single-Sign-On.
6	GitLab	Git Repository	Integrated with Single-Sign-On.
7	Hadoop HDFS	Big Data Storage System	Through Pilot Codes.
8	Ktirio GUI	Simulation Configurator	Integrated with Single-Sign-On.
9	MathSO Portal	Workflow Orchestrator	Integrated with Single-Sign-On.
10	QCG Portal	Workflow Orchestrator	Integrated with Single-Sign-On.
12	Argos Suite	Energy Management	To be Integrated
13	NIFI	Data Transfer System	Through WFOs

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	17 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Most of the supporting services are connected as a direct link but going through HiDALGO2’s Single-Sign-On and Identity management solution, Keycloak. This can be bypassed for guest access. A screenshot of the current state and looking at how the services are presented via the HiDALGO2 Dashboard is shown in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Supporting Services in Dashboard

There is also a special focus on the HiDALGO2 pilot simulation codes, which are accessed through “cards” that represent the pilot code, as shown in Figure 8. Clicking on the “info” icon of the “Urban Air Pollution” pilot (UAP) card opens a description text, while if the user clicks the “Run” icon instead, then the user is taken to the MathSO portal, with arrangements for running the UAP code. This sequence is detailed in the upcoming sections of the deliverable, in Section 4.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	18 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 8. Pilot Code services in the Dashboard

3.1.2 External services

In addition to the internal HiDALGO2 ecosystem, the Dashboard will also look to connect and integrate with external services that provide utility to either HiDALGO2’s developers and users, or to the wider HPC and general user community. This includes new and upcoming EuroHPC Federation Platform⁰, the LEXIS portal⁰, and the HPC-In-Europe⁰ central hub. Other communities and portals will also be considered in the future.

3.2 User and right management

The HiDALGO2 ecosystem uses Keycloak, provided through the HiDALGO2 IDM service, as the common identity and access-management solution for most integrated services. The Dashboard relies on the same identity layer which makes the Dashboard part of the common HiDALGO2 authentication environment rather than an isolated application with independent user handling.

The Dashboard uses identity information, roles, groups and organization membership to decide which entries and management functions are available to a user. While Keycloak access with SSO enables access to most services, some need their own

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	19 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

service level configuration for access, like Hadoop HDF or the training cluster. Other services may need additional configuration for tighter integration, such as CKAN, and JupyterHub and pilot-specific tools. User and rights management must therefore be understood as a combination of Dashboard-level visibility, Keycloak-based SSO and service-specific resource permissions.

3.2.1 Authentication levels

The HiDALGO2 Dashboard uses Keycloak as its identity and access-management service. Authentication follows the OpenID Connect authorization-code flow. When a user logs in, the Dashboard redirects the user to the HiDALGO2 IDM service. After successful authentication, the Dashboard receives an access token and can use the active session to call protected backend services and selected workflow-orchestrator APIs. The backend validates the token before processing authenticated operations.

The Dashboard distinguishes between several practical access levels.

Guest users can browse entries explicitly marked as public and can access services that allow unauthenticated or guest access.

Authenticated users can access entries intended for signed-in users and can use personal Dashboard functions, such as pinned items, recently used items, saved layouts and stored preferences.

Internal users can access consortium-internal services when the corresponding role, group or organization membership is present.

Administrators can access cross-organization management functions and maintain catalogue entries beyond a single organization.

Dashboard entries contain access metadata. The `guest` and `onlyguest` properties determine whether an entry is shown to anonymous users, authenticated users or both. The optional `roles` property restricts an entry to users holding at least one of the listed Keycloak roles or groups. Organization-specific entries can be associated with a Keycloak organization or group. This enables the catalogue to contain public services, consortium-internal services, external-partner services and pilot- or institution-specific entries without maintaining separate Dashboard deployments.

The implementation recognizes the administrative role `hidalgo2-admins`. The `hidalgo2-internal-user` role is used for consortium-internal services. Administrators can access cross-organization management functions, while ordinary authenticated users are limited to their own organizations and personal data. External partners are assigned to the appropriate external organization or group so that their access can be managed separately from internal consortium users.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	20 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

3.2.2 User registration and management

User accounts and credentials are managed centrally in the HiDALGO2 IDM service rather than in the Dashboard database. The Dashboard provides a login action, but it does not implement its own password database or independent registration form. Password policies, credential recovery, account activation and identity verification therefore remain responsibilities of the configured Keycloak realm.

At the current stage, registration of new users is handled manually by administrators. Self-registration could technically be enabled in Keycloak by activating user registration, e-mail verification and default role assignment. However, before this can be used generally, a controlled approval process is needed to assign users to the appropriate role, organization and service-access groups.

External access should be granted only for clearly defined use cases. Guest access is sufficient for public information, documentation, training material and public Dashboard entries. A registered external account is needed when pilot owners want to provide selected stakeholders, potential customers, students, reviewers or other EuroHPC users with access to protected demonstrations, training scenarios or pilot-related services. For the time being, such access should be granted only through the HiDALGO2 Keycloak instance, using an `external_user` role and the appropriate institute, pilot, training or external-organization group.

Access decisions should be made by service and tested first on the prototyping machine. Public and training-oriented services may be opened to external users where the corresponding owner approves the scenario. Operational and infrastructure-level services should remain protected: **Keycloak/IDM** administration because it controls accounts and roles; **Zabbix** because it exposes monitoring and infrastructure information; **Open Project** and **HedgeDoc** because they may contain internal planning notes and draft material; **Altair and Eagle HPC** because direct compute access must remain controlled through WFOs and proper project application at the HPC service site, for now; **GitLab** because only public repositories should be externally visible; **ARGOS Energy Management Suite** because it may expose operational energy data; and **NiFi** because it controls internal data-transfer workflows.

For user-facing services such as the Dashboard, MathSO Portal, QCG Portal, CKAN, JupyterHub, Moodle, AskBot, Zammad, Wiki and Ktirio GUI, access should depend on the scenario. A training user may need Moodle, selected documentation and a controlled workflow application. A potential customer may need only a pilot demonstration and selected result data. A EuroHPC user may need a WFO application, CKAN dataset and approved execution environment. In all cases, the Dashboard should expose only the services required for the approved use case.

In future releases, the process should evolve towards a guided registration and approval workflow, where external users request access, verify their e-mail address,

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	21 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

state their intended use case, and receive the relevant Keycloak groups only after approval by the responsible pilot or service owner.

3.2.3 Onboarding of new users

New visitors can explore the public parts of the Dashboard without authentication. Users who need protected HiDALGO2 services must sign in through the HiDALGO2 IDM service.

At the current stage, onboarding is handled manually because access to the HiDALGO2 ecosystem involves several connected services, not only the Dashboard. Depending on the use case, a user may need an IDM account, CKAN organization membership and API key, SSH keys for the training cluster or JupyterHub, Kerberos access for HDFS, MathSO or QCG WFO credential registration, and access to pilot-specific tools such as the Ktirio GUI.

External users are handled with additional care. Access is granted only for a defined purpose, such as training, pilot demonstration, stakeholder evaluation, potential-customer testing or selected EuroHPC use. Before access is provided, the pilot responsible or service provider must approve the use case, and a HiDALGO2 administrator must approve and perform the account and group assignment. External users receive only the roles and groups required for the approved scenario.

Institution-wide access for external organizations is not granted at this stage. External users are added individually or through controlled external groups, and their access is limited to the relevant pilot, training or demonstration environment.

In future releases, this manual procedure should be replaced or supported by a guided onboarding workflow, where users can request access, state their intended use case, and receive access only after approval by both the pilot provider and a HiDALGO2 administrator.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	22 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

4 Pilot integration into the Dashboard

4.1 UAP

The Urban Air Pilot is represented in the Dashboard by two complementary entries. Anonymous visitors see the Urban Air Pilot Description entry, which introduces the use case and links to the public HiDALGO2 Urban Air project page. Authenticated users are presented with the Urban Air Pilot Deployment entry.

Selecting the run action does not embed the complete simulation interface inside the Dashboard. Instead, the Dashboard opens the MathSO Portal application catalogue in a new browser tab using the URL <https://portal.hidalgo2.eu/application?tags=uap>. The tag query restricts the catalogue to UAP-related applications. This approach keeps high-level discovery and ecosystem navigation in the Dashboard while delegating application configuration, HPC selection, execution monitoring and result handling to the specialised workflow Portal.

4.1.1 Technical details of integration

Integration and user flow details all three main UAP applications separately: RedSIM, Xyst and UAP-FOAM. All three applications, while integrated fully into the MathSO portal, have separate methods of deployment, and level of detail in configurability. All applications are integrated as a workflow application described by a TOSCA-style YAML blueprint. These blueprints define user-visible inputs, hidden helper scripts, workflow tasks, task dependencies and expected default types. At execution time, the Portal backend creates an execution record and passes the resolved workflow to the orchestrator, which prepares the remote working directory, transfers the necessary files and executes the tasks in dependency order.

RedSIM

The current RedSIM workflow obtains the solver source from the SZE HiDALGO2 RedSIM repository at <https://github.com/sze-hidalgo-2/RedSIM.git>. During deployment, the repository is cloned into the execution working directory, the CPU build script is invoked, and the workflow verifies that the `redsim_mpi_cpu` executable has been produced before continuing. The blueprint also supports CKAN-based input material, with repository and dataset selections resolved from the authenticated user's configured data repositories and transferred into the workflow workspace.

The geometric input is selected through an interactive map field, which stores the selected bounding box and optional points of interest in `map_data/map.json`. A meshing script reads these coordinates and calls the UAP mesher service. User-configurable meshing parameters include building merge thresholds and spatial resolutions for buildings, terrain and the top of the domain. The generated artefacts include `urban_domain.mesh`, `domain_surface.obj` and, where available, `buildings.stl`.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	23 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Before simulation, preprocessing tasks generate the RedSIM Lua configuration and the Slurm job script. The Lua file imports the generated urban mesh, defines the wind-direction series, sets parameters such as angular increment, number of directions, CFL number, spatial order and number of exported time steps, and configures EnSight Gold output. The Slurm script resolves the selected HPC resources, exports the OpenMP thread count and starts `redsim_mpi_cpu` with `srun`.

The workflow is represented as an explicit dependency graph. Meshing and compilation are completed before configuration generation, the solver starts only after the Lua and Slurm configurations are available, and post-processing depends on successful simulation completion. This allows the orchestrator to stop dependent tasks when an earlier stage fails and to report the failing stage to the user. Task states and deployment progress are recorded in the Portal and can also be summarized in the authenticated Dashboard integration.

RedSIM writes its numerical output under the RedSim-out directory. For each simulated wind direction, the solver produces EnSight Gold data. A post-processing script searches the output for case files, selects velocity magnitude as the preferred scalar field, and generates PNG images for the simulated directions. These images are uploaded to the UAP mesher/result service using the workflow execution identifier, and the service can generate an angle grid. The Portal recognises the PNG expected-result declaration and provides an image viewer with individual and grid views, navigation, zooming, rotation, slideshow playback and download functions.

For interactive 3D visualisation, the workflow processes the complete RedSim-out directory together with available context geometry, such as `buildings.stl` and `domain_surface.obj`. It generates the CFDR configuration files, compresses the visualization directory, and stores the resulting ZIP archive as the main `redsim_cfdr` result. The expected-result metadata configures the 3D viewer, including the default velocity-magnitude variable, color map, slice positions and building geometry. After completion, the Portal presents both PNG and 3D actions, while logs and result archives remain linked to the deployment through the common execution identifier.

Xyst

The current Xyst workflow executes the solver from a Singularity image selected by the user from CKAN. Instead of compiling the solver during deployment, the workflow retrieves the selected container image and uses it as the execution environment. This makes the deployment reproducible and allows different Xyst versions or preconfigured execution environments to be provided as CKAN-managed resources.

The input mesh is also selected from CKAN and transferred into the execution working directory. Xyst is executed through its Inciter tool, which uses a Lua control file for the simulation setup and supports mesh-based engineering-flow simulations. The workflow exposes this Lua configuration file in an editable text field, allowing the user to review or modify the numerical setup before deployment.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	24 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

During execution, the workflow deploys the selected container image, input mesh and edited configuration file, then generates and submits the corresponding job script through the workflow orchestrator. The dependency structure ensures that all required inputs are available before the solver task starts, and that failures are reported at the corresponding workflow stage.

The numerical output, diagnostics and execution logs remain associated with the deployment. Depending on the configured result policy, selected outputs may be archived to CKAN or another configured repository, keeping the container image, mesh, configuration file, results and logs linked through the workflow execution identifier.

UAP-FOAM

The current UAP-FOAM workflow uses containerized deployment. The required container image is prepared as part of the workflow execution environment, while the input mesh can be selected and downloaded before the simulation starts. This allows users to reuse prepared urban meshes and run the OpenFOAM-based simulation in a reproducible environment.

The MathSO instance configuration interface exposes the main simulation parameters to the user. These include the emission setup, which can be disabled or selected as traffic-based or point-source emission, wind parameters, probe locations, simulation time and selected OpenFOAM parameters. The workflow converts these settings into the corresponding simulation configuration before submitting the job.

After the required inputs and configuration files are prepared, the workflow generates the execution script and submits the simulation through the workflow orchestrator. The orchestrator tracks the deployment state, records logs and reports progress to the Portal and Dashboard.

After completion, the results generated can be inspected through post-processing and visualization actions. The workflow supports both two-dimensional image outputs and an interactive three-dimensional view, allowing users to analyze the simulation results directly from the connected portal environment.

4.1.2 Sequence of user flow

All UAP-based workflows are reachable through the Dashboard. A visitor may open the **Urban Air Pilot Description** card to read public information about the pilot. To execute simulations, the user needs to be authenticated through Keycloak. After login, the Dashboard will evaluate the user's roles and organization membership, and displays the **Urban Air Pilot Deployment**, when eligible. After selecting the run action on the UAP deployment card, the MathSO portal is opened with all applications with the uap tags. Below are the descriptions of how the separate applications are executed within the MathSO portal.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	25 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 9. Selecting simulation domain for RedSIM within Stockholm city for wind comfort calculations

RedSIM

To configure RedSIM, the user may run an already created instance or create a new one. The instance form is generated from the workflow blueprint. The proper simulation area is to be selected, as shown in Figure 9. Selecting simulation domain for RedSIM within Stockholm city for wind comfort calculations along with RedSIM parameters. Additionally, CKAN input and output repositories are to be selected and finally the instance configuration is saved.

Xyst

Xyst is configured through an editable Lua control file associated with the selected CKAN mesh and Singularity image. The workflow presents this file in the MathSO configuration interface, as shown in Figure 10, so that users can adjust the numerical setup before deployment. In the default lid-driven cavity example, important parameters include the final simulation time term, terminal-output interval `ttyi`, CFL number `cfl`, solver selection `solver = "chocg"`, numerical flux flux = "damp4", Runge–Kutta order `rk`, partitioning method `part = "rcb"`, Reynolds number `Re`, material viscosity in `mat`, and the iteration limits, tolerances and preconditioners in the momentum and pressure blocks. Initial and boundary conditions are defined through `ic`, `bc_noslip`, `bc_sym`, `bc_dir` and `bc_dirval`, while `fieldout` and `diag` control field-output and diagnostic-output frequency. Xyst’s documentation describes Inciter configuration as being parsed from command-line and control-file input, with Lua used for control-file parsing.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	26 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 10. Configuration interface for Xyst within the MathSO portal

UAP-FOAM

UAP-FOAM is configured through the MathSO instance configuration interface before deployment. The user selects the containerized execution environment and the input mesh, then tunes the main simulation settings exposed by the workflow. These include the emission model, which can be disabled or configured as traffic-based or point-source emission, wind parameters, probe locations, total simulation time and selected UAP-FOAM and OpenFOAM parameters, as partly shown on Figure 11. The workflow translates these values into the corresponding UAP-FOAM case configuration `uap_foam.cfg` and prepares the applications internal three-step workflow: converting input data to OpenFOAM-readable files, including the mesh; decomposing the mesh into the appropriate number of subdomains; and executing the proper UAP-FOAM parallel applications.

Execution and viewing of the results

To execute any of the above applications, a user starts by opening the execution view in the MathSO Portal, selecting the UAP application and the corresponding instance. Before launching the workflow, the user chooses an available HPC configuration and reviews the resolved execution parameters. This step allows the user to confirm that the selected application, input settings and target execution environment are consistent. If the selected HPC login requires an interactive second authentication factor, the Portal requests the additional authentication input before the workflow can continue.

The orchestrator then executes the workflow steps in their defined order. During the full execution, progress information and task states remain associated with the deployment, making it possible to identify the current stage of the workflow and any failing step.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	27 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 11. Configuring emission type within the UAP-FOAM configuration panel of the MathSO portal. No emission, point source, and EMI-file based emission may be selected.

The user can follow the execution in the MathSO Portal. The Portal indicates whether the deployment is ready, running, completed, failed or cancelled, and provides detailed progress and log information. In addition, the Dashboard can display aggregated Portal activity and active-job information for the authenticated user.

Figure 12. Demonstrating the 3D results of a RedSIM simulation within CFDRe, opened from the MathSO portal.

After successful completion, the user can open the deployment results. The PNG action opens the generated directional images, while the 3D action launches the configured viewer for the EnSight Gold results and the associated urban context geometry, as depicted on Figure 12. Logs and result archives can also be downloaded or accessed from the configured repository.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	28 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

4.2 UB

The Urban Building (UB) pilot has been integrated into the HiDALGO2 Dashboard through the MathSO workflow orchestration service. It is comprised of two tools, the GUI and the application. The integration of UB into the Dashboard provides access to Ktirio WASM, where users can create and prepare their data, as well as an interface for running and managing KUB simulations. Secondly through this Dashboard, users can access HPC machines and run very large-scale simulations on the machine of their choice.

4.2.1 Technical details of integration

The execution of a Ktirio Urban Building simulation within the HPC environment is structured into two distinct phases:

- **Phase 1: Preprocessing (Mesh Partitioning)** This initial step prepares the generated data for High-Performance Computing. It efficiently distributes terrain, buildings, and vegetation entities across the compute nodes.
- **Phase 2: Simulate (Physical Calculations)** Following the preprocessing, the core simulation phase is executed. This step performs the heavy physical calculations required for the chosen scenario. It includes computing solar masks and solving the physical equations governing the thermal and energetic behaviour of the buildings. The post-processing phase is included in the simulation and is executed at each time step.

In MathSO orchestration environment, the Ktirio Urban Building application is represented through a YAML workflow description format. This blueprint defines the application’s lifecycle and automates the transition between the Dashboard and the HPC compute nodes. The Dashboard interacts with MathSO by passing user-defined configurations, such as dataset URLs, required API keys (eg., for other DMPs than CKAN), and custom step scripts directly into this YAML blueprint.

Once initiated, the workflow executes automatically in three sequential stages.

- **First, the environment preparation.** The system automatically downloads the required Apptainer image and pulls the necessary datasets (geographic data, meshes, weather, and FMU physical models). Data is securely transferred from remote Data Management Plans (DMPs) such as the HiDALGO2 CKAN server.
- **Second, the pre-processing.** The system partitions the simulation domain (as described in Phase 1) based on the number of HPC cores allocated for the job.
- **Third, the simulation execution.** Distributed computing tasks are submitted to the HPC nodes via the SLURM workload manager using standard SBATCH directives.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	29 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

The integration into the HiDALGO2 Dashboard is highly streamlined thanks to Ktirio’s native CemDB architecture and versioning system, which manages the data flow via dedicated CLI suites:

- **Location Datasets:** These datasets (e.g. “strasbourg”) contain geographic data (GIS, JSON, meshes), weather CSVs, and occupancy scenarios. To guarantee data integrity and strict versioning during transfers, every dataset includes a manifest.json file containing schema versions, KUB compatibility checks, and SHA-256 checksums for all files. A specific .cfg file defines location-specific parameters, such as the partitioning logic applied during pre-processing. The kub-dataset CLI command suite manages the entire lifecycle of this data, handling packing, unpacking, pushing, pulling and manifest regeneration.
- **Simulator Datasets:** Unlike location data, these are automatically generated via the CLI (kub-dataset generate simulator) and contain the physical models (FMUs) categorized by Level of Detail (LOD0, LOD1).
- **Job Management:** The kub-simulate CLI acts as the launcher helper. It acts as the bridge between the containerized Apptainer runtime and the HPC scheduler, managing Slurm job submissions and tracking the status of running simulations.

Concerning visualization and post-run analysis, Ktirio features the kub-dashboard, a read-only web interface dedicated to exploring the results and location data generated by the simulations. Through this interface, users can access:

- **Run Catalog:** Allows users to browse and filter specific simulation runs (single or ensemble).
- **Location Explorer:** Enables the analysis of building inventory statistics, weather heatmaps (Heating/Cooling Degree Days), and interactive 3D maps using Paraview export.
- **KPI Playbook:** Utilizes a registry of specifications to render plots and interpret complex simulation results against defined thermal and energetic thresholds.

4.2.2 Sequence of user flow

4.2.2.1 Accesing the UB Pilot.

The user can access the UB pilot through the HiDALGO2 Dashboard. The “Go to” button takes the user to the Ktirio WASM page, where they can access the graphical interface to create simulation data. The “Run Application” button redirects the user to the MathSO orchestration environment, where they can run KUB calculations on the HPC machine of their choice.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	30 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 13. Accessing UB pilot in HiDALGO2 Dashboard

4.2.2.2 Creating a Simulation Instance

Once the user has selected the Ktirio Urban Building application, they can create a new simulation instance by choosing a location dataset. This location dataset contains data such as meshes; weather or occupation scenarios generated from the Ktirio GUI and is stored on data-platform CKAN. Users can then retrieve the dataset they previously generated via the GUI or select an existing location dataset to simulate the same dataset using different scenarios or parameters.

Figure 14. Figure Ktirio WASM Graphical Interface

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	31 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Another way to create a new instance is to do so from Ktirio WASM if the user has created a new dataset by calling the MathSO Portal API. This simplifies the process, and the user simply needs to select the instance they just created from the Dashboard. Next, once the location dataset has been selected, the user must choose a simulation scenario (for example, simulating a heat wave) and simulation parameters (start time, end time, physical models used, enable visualization, etc.).

4.2.2.3 Configure HPC

Once the instance is setup, the user selects the HPC system to compute the simulation. They specify the number of computation nodes and number of tasks by node to launch to submit the simulation to the scheduler of the HPC machine.

4.2.2.4 Monitoring experiments

Users can view all the simulations they have run, along with the creation date, execution time, and the machine on which they were run in the “Experiments” tab. In addition, in cemdb, each dataset has a “simulations” subfolder containing all the simulations the user has run, along with manifest.json, provenance.json ensuring run reproducibility.

4.2.2.5 Viewing Results and Retrieving Outputs

During simulation KPIs are aggregated as they are calculated. They can be visualized using different tools: Python notebook analysing the city’s energy and thermal results, as well as Paraview exports to visualize in 3D results if visualization was enabled at the start of the simulation and building kpi files.

This data can be transferred either to CKAN or via an SSH connection to another machine.

4.3 RES

The Renewable Energy Sources (RES) pilot has been instantiated through a dedicated domain-specific application template implemented in the QCG workflow orchestrator and made available in the HiDALGO2 Dashboard. The recently redesigned mechanism of application templates in QCG (described in detail in D2.6) allowed us to prepare an interface adjusted for the final stakeholders of the Pilot. Consequently, the interface ensures high level of User eXperience (UX) and consistently covers all stages of the typical Pilot’s usage, including definition of the input parameters, fully automated execution of the workflow, monitoring of its progress and the embedded means for the appealing visualization of the results.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	32 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

4.3.1 Technical details of integration

QCG's architecture clearly distinguishes the development of application templates from their usage. In order to meet the expectations of end-users, the templates are created by a QCG administrator or another person experienced in template development. They translate the requirements of the application representatives into a final solution encompassing both the GUI and the workflow execution. This process enables the building of services tailored for end-customers in a Software as a Service (SaaS) model, where the interface design can be highly customized and adjusted to specific stakeholders.

The process of creating an application template is twofold. First, with the help of the provided Application Template Builder (see D2.6 for details), custom views for a pilot are created. In the case of the RES application, the following views were developed:

- Input specification Form
- Global view for a workflow progress monitoring
- Views representing monitoring of execution of individual steps of a workflow, namely:
 - Initialization
 - Preprocessing
 - RES.WRF
 - RES.Eulag
 - RES.Analysis
- A view on the presentation of results.

These views make use of generic components and layouts designed to match the needs of not only the RES application, but also other use cases. The current list of components includes progress indicators, charts, image grids, and maps.

The prepared layouts are then exported in a JSON format and integrated into the Python codebase of the template, which constitutes the second step of the process. This programmatic definition of a template's execution, combined with full control over the integration logic between the frontend layer and the execution component, allows us to build sophisticated execution scenarios that support uncommon, dynamic interactions between the GUI and the computational backend. For instance, the RES template input form can dynamically detect and display the current availability of input datasets or the real-time status of computational resources.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	33 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

4.3.2 Sequence of user flow

The RES pilot packages the entire simulation around the practical expectations of final stakeholders, such as businesses and public institutions, and provides as a comprehensive SaaS solution covering all phases of its execution life cycle.

4.3.2.1 Step 1: Accessing the RES Pilot

The RES Pilot can be accessed easily from the HiDALGO2 Dashboard or, alternatively, via the direct link to the RES input form in the QCG portal¹.

Figure 15. RES Entry in HiDALGO2 Dashboard

4.3.2.2 Step 2: Configuring simulation parameters

In line with the core idea of simplifying the user interface, configuring the RES simulation is reduced to selecting just a few essential parameters: simulation start time, simulation duration, simulation location. This simplified input is enough for the RES pilot, as based on the provided parameters the whole configuration of simulations models, including geometry, required data, physics schemes, resolution, or timestep are automatically assigned.

The location can be easily selected using an interactive map component integrated directly into the form. Among others, the form provides built-in features for validation of provided input.

This form can be extended depending on needs and specific flavour of the RES execution, tailored for scientists, public bodies, energy operators, individuals.

Once configured, the scenario can be easily submitted for the execution on HPC resources by clicking the “Submit” button. The collected parameters are packaged and sent to the QCG backend services for further execution orchestration.

¹ <https://qcg.hidalgo2.eu/ui/submit?templateUrl=core/hidalgo2/res>

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	34 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 16. RES Simulation Parameters (light mode)

4.3.2.3 Step 3: RES workflow execution

From a conceptual standpoint, the RES workflow is static in nature. It executes a predefined sequence of steps with resource requirements that are largely known in advance. These characteristics allow us to effectively utilize the built-in workflow orchestration mechanism of the QCG system. Consequently, the RES execution logic is contained within a few Python files that comprehensively define the underlying infrastructure-level routines in combination with workflow-specific user-facing graphical components.

Table 3. Steps of the RES workflow executed in QCG

Step	Infrastructure Execution	Monitoring
Initialisation	Workflow submission	Workflow progress (through whole simulation)
Preprocessing	Download required data to initialize models (UI node, fast storage)	Progress bar
RES.WRF	Execution of WRF-based RES module (moderate number of computational nodes)	Progress bar, with the visible progress of internal RES.WRF processing.
RES.Eulag	Execution of Eulag-based RES module (large number of computational nodes)	Progress bar, with the visible progress of internal RES.EULAG processing and the iteratively generated images presenting current simulation results.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	35 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

RES.Analysis	Analysis of collected results (low number of computational nodes or node with GPU or node with large memory)	Presentation of the progress of execution, typically instantly replaced with the presentation of the analysis results.
Postprocessing	Upload of the results data to CKAN. (UI node)	Currently not monitored, background task.

QCG manages the proper execution of individual steps by mapping them to the most suitable infrastructure resources. Data transfers required for RES are performed on a single node with access to a fast storage. The simulations models are dispatched to dedicated nodes for intensive computational tasks, considering their different requirements for CPUs and memory. The analysis step is dispatched to large memory nodes for HPDA processing, while AI-based analysis is submitted to GPU nodes.

Figure 17. RES workflow execution progress monitoring (dark mode)

Through the close integration of workflow execution with the QCG GUI, it was possible to provide a consistent and visually appealing view for monitoring the RES workflow's progress. A standout UX feature of the QCG workflow mechanism is its built-in automated presentation of the most relevant information to the user. Thus, during execution, the user is automatically directed to the view showing the progress of the currently active step. Once the workflow is completed, the system seamlessly displays the final results.

The currently presented monitoring data and its form are results of discussions with the RES Pilot developers, but they can be easily extended or modified by the adaptation of application template. Table 3. Steps of the RES workflow executed in

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	36 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

QCG provides a brief description of each step in the RES workflow, detailing how they are executed on the infrastructure and how they are currently monitored in the GUI.

4.3.2.4 Step 4: RES results presentation

The analytical results of the RES pilot are displayed immediately after the final workflow step completes. Currently, these results feature key summary metrics about the produced energy alongside charts that visualize critical simulation data over time. Much like the monitoring interfaces, this results presentation view can be easily customized to meet specific user needs.

Figure 18. RES analysis results (light mode)

4.4 WF

Deployed directly within the HiDALGO2 Dashboard, the Wildfires pilot is powered by a dedicated, domain-specific application template built on the QCG workflow orchestrator. Because this implementation closely mirrors the architecture designed for the RES pilot, section 4.3 RES serves as a valuable reference. However, two main conceptual differences can be recognised. First, the data management strategy is different: while RES uses a simpler data handling approach based on data accessed directly from the web and uploaded to CKAN, the WF pilot requires the specialized HiDALGO2 Data Transfer Library² to be incorporated. Second, although the WF

² https://pypi.org/project/hid_data_transfer_lib/

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	37 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

interface should deliver the similar components for parameter specification and clear, visual progress monitoring during execution, it does not need to display the final outputs by itself; instead, these results are handled by a separate toolbox.

4.4.1 Technical details of integration

The WF pilot follows the same template development approach as the RES pilot described in Section 4.3, with layouts created using the Application Template Builder and then integrated into the template’s Python codebase. This approach is used to develop the following specialised views:

- Input specification form
- Global view for a workflow progress monitoring
- Views representing monitoring of execution of individual steps of a Workflow
 - Initialization
 - Preprocessing (Download input data, optionally deploy models)
 - WPS
 - WRF-Sfire
 - Postprocessing (Upload output data)

At this stage of development, the Input Specification view is fully implemented according to the pilot requirements. Due to workflow similarities, the execution monitoring views will leverage generic mechanisms developed for the RES pilot. The only difference is the final view, which will present a simple link to the generated results for opening in a dedicated external application.

In terms of data management, WF workflow execution utilizes the HiDALGO2 Data Transfer Library to programmatically access Hadoop data spaces, where the pilot’s input and output data are stored. This integration is embedded directly into the Python codebase of the template; thus, it remains transparent to the user, who only needs to provide access credentials for the data management services.

4.4.2 Sequence of user flow

For the WF pilot’s target users, who may be policy makers under time and stress pressure, the intuitiveness and easiness of running simulations is a key aspect. Therefore, in constructing the interface for the execution of the pilot in QCG workflow orchestrator, our goal was to provide highly user-friendly interface and comprehensive automation. Consequently, a user is provided with clean and minimalistic views for specification of input parameters and then for the monitoring of the progress of the execution.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	38 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

4.4.2.1 Step 1: Accessing the WF Pilot

The WF pilot can be easily accessed either from the HiDALGO2 Dashboard or via a direct link to the WF input form in the QCG portal³.

Figure 19. WF Entry in HiDALGO2 Dashboard

4.4.2.2 Step 2: Configuring access credentials

Firstly, to execute a workflow through QCG, users must configure a few global settings related to their data management access, i.e. Kerberos and NIFI server access credentials. This is a one-time operation that is not part of the daily use of the pilot. Currently, these settings are configured through environment variables set manually on an HPC machine, but future integration will also allow configuration directly from QCG.

4.4.2.3 Step 3: Configuring simulation input parameters

The configuration of simulation input parameters for the workflow is intentionally simplified to just a few essential settings. In the first phase, presented in Figure 20, the user configures the following options:

- **Scenario time** – the simulation timeframe.
- **Simulation resolution** – currently, 120 m and 200 m resolutions are supported. Other resolutions may be considered in the future but these have been selected at this stage to facilitate a smooth execution of the simulation
- **Pollution** – the type of pollutant, selected from a predefined list. The system makes it possible to assess the dispersion of the main pollutants in the smoke generated by the wildfire.
- **Simulation area** – the geographic area for the simulation.

³ <https://qcg.hidalgo2.eu/ui/submit?templateUrl=core/hidalgo2/wf>

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	39 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

The workflow template restricts the simulation area to locations with available fuel data, providing clear guidance on eligible options.

Figure 20. WF Input parameters specification form - general settings

In the second phase after selecting the simulation area, the user can define up to five ignition points within its boundaries as outlined in Figure 21. For each ignition point, in addition to its coordinates, the user must specify the point activity time period. The UI assists users in this process by suggesting initial start and end times and prevents values from exceeding the simulation runtime.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	40 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Phase 2 —

Defining fires on the map

← [Return to applications list](#)

Wildfires scenario definition

Complete all fields below to submit task.

Scenario time

18.06.2026

📅

12:33

🕒

—

25.06.2026

📅

16:59

🕒

Simulation resolution

120 m

200 m

Pollution

Select pollution type

Simulation area

+ Add point

Remove area

+

-

🔥

Point 1

42,82783444

N

-6,41100466

E

📄

✕

Time of fire

18.06.2026

📅

12:33

🕒

—

25.06.2026

📅

16:59

🕒

🔥

Point 2

42,56925486

N

-6,88318148

E

📄

✕

Time of fire

18.06.2026

📅

12:33

🕒

—

25.06.2026

📅

16:59

🕒

Cancel

Submit

4 Add point / Remove area — quick scenario management.

2 Two points — each point is a separate fire source.

1 Area selection — mark the risk zone.

3 Point parameters — coordinates and start/end time.

Figure 21. WF Input parameters specification form - ignition points set-up

Once all parameters are set-up, the scenario can be easily submitted for the execution. During the submission process, all the settings are converted from the JSON document into a format supported by the WF execution scripts. An example such file is shown in Figure 22.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services	Page:	41 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU
	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Phase 3 — Output after Submit

```

params:
  dx: 200
  dy: 200
  end_date: "2026-06-25"
  end_hour: "16:59:00"
fire_ignitions:
  fire_ignition_end_lat1: 43.00095457
  fire_ignition_end_lat2: 43.31375939
  fire_ignition_end_lat3: 42.92451602
  fire_ignition_end_lat4: 0
  fire_ignition_end_lat5: 0
  fire_ignition_end_lon1: -6.11727053
  fire_ignition_end_lon2: -6.40277279
  fire_ignition_end_lon3: -6.33688765
  fire_ignition_end_lon4: 0
  fire_ignition_end_lon5: 0
  fire_ignition_end_time1: 1782399540
  fire_ignition_end_time2: 1782399540
  fire_ignition_end_time3: 1782399540
  fire_ignition_end_time4: 0
  fire_ignition_end_time5: 0
  fire_ignition_start_lat1: 43.00095457
  fire_ignition_start_lat2: 43.31375939
  fire_ignition_start_lat3: 42.92451602
  fire_ignition_start_lat4: 0
  fire_ignition_start_lat5: 0
  fire_ignition_start_lon1: -6.11727053
  fire_ignition_start_lon2: -6.40277279
  fire_ignition_start_lon3: -6.33688765
  fire_ignition_start_lon4: 0
  fire_ignition_start_lon5: 0
  fire_ignition_start_time1: 1781778780
  fire_ignition_start_time2: 1781778780
  fire_ignition_start_time3: 1781778780
  fire_ignition_start_time4: 0
  fire_ignition_start_time5: 0
  fire_num_ignitions: 3
[[Prototype]]: Object
pollution: "pm25"
ref_lat: 43.079743326666666
ref_lon: -6.285643656666667
start_date: "2026-06-18"
start_hour: "12:33:00"

```

- 1

Scenario parameters — dates, times, resolution, and pollutant

They define the simulation time range, the grid resolution (dx, dy), and the pollutant type.
- 2

fire_ignitions — data for up to 5 ignition points

For each point (max. 5):

 - start coordinates (lat, lon)
 - end coordinates (lat, lon)
 - start and end timestamps (UNIX)

The field `fire_num_ignitions` indicates the number of active ignition points.
- 3

Coordinates and timestamps — complete input configuration

Reference parameters (`ref_lat`, `ref_lon`) and the simulation start time (`start_date`, `start_hour`) form the complete input configuration of the scenario.
- 4

Payload ready to be sent to the backend / further processing

A parameter set compliant with the API schema — ready to be sent and used to start the simulation.

Result: the system returns a complete set of scenario parameters

Figure 22. JSON file generated by the WF GUI during submission.

4.4.2.4 Step 4: Workflow execution

The submitted workflow is routed for execution to one of the resources supporting the pilot. While resource selection is currently hardcoded, this process will eventually be fully automated, driven by resource availability and user preferences.

The individual workflow steps are performed accordingly with their resource requirements either on a single node (download and upload of data) or using multi-node allocation (computational jobs).

In the current development phase of the template, workflow execution can be monitored at a high level through the global view of submitted tasks as presented in Figure 23. However, work is underway to develop a full-featured monitoring system like the one proposed for RES (see Section 4.3.2.3).

As mentioned earlier, our goal is to expand the functionality in the near future to give users greater freedom in selecting simulation options and to expand the selectable geographic area, which is currently limited by the availability of fuel model data.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	42 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 23. WF workflow execution monitoring in QCG

4.5 MTW

The Material Transport in Water (MTW) pilot is integrated into the HiDALGO2 Dashboard through the MathSO Workflow Orchestration (WFO) service. Through a unified interface, users can configure, execute, monitor, and retrieve MTW simulations on EuroHPC systems, while application-specific and infrastructure-related details are managed transparently by MathSO.

4.5.1 Technical details of integration

Within MathSO, MTW is represented as an application blueprint (Figure 24 left) that abstracts application-specific implementation details from the end user. The blueprint defines the user-configurable inputs, execution workflow, and target HPC interactions, providing a consistent interface for simulation management across different computing systems.

The application blueprint separates user interaction from the underlying execution environment. Simulation parameters are exposed through configurable input categories and are translated into the native MTW parameter format during execution. Users can select predefined simulation setups from connected repositories and customize numerical, physical, and output-related parameters through the graphical interface. This approach simplifies experiment configuration while preserving compatibility with the underlying MTW framework.

Execution of MTW simulations is realized through a workflow consisting of preparation, execution, and post-processing stages. MathSO automatically generates the required configuration files, prepares the execution environment, submits the simulation to the target HPC scheduler, and collects the resulting outputs. The workflow orchestration

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	43 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 24. (left) MTW Application Blueprint; (right) HPC Configuration Overview

layer therefore eliminates the need for direct interaction with cluster-specific submission scripts and system commands.

Data management is integrated through repositories accessible from MathSO, including CKAN-based catalogues and user-defined storage locations on HPC systems. These repositories are used to manage application binaries, simulation configurations, and generated outputs. Access to HPC resources is abstracted through reusable HPC configurations (Figure 24 left) that encapsulate system-specific information such as authentication methods, scheduler settings, software environments, and resource allocation parameters. This abstraction enables the same MTW workflow to be executed on different HPC systems with minimal changes to the application definition.

Figure 25. (left) MTW Dashboard Entry; (right) HPC Resource Availability

4.5.2 Sequence of user flow

The MTW pilot workflow has been designed to guide users through the complete lifecycle of a simulation experiment, from initial configuration to result retrieval. A video tutorial demonstrating the orchestration of MTW runs using MathSO is also available on YouTube⁴.

⁴ MTW user workflow video tutorial on YouTube: <https://youtu.be/rowCuXBwzb8>.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	44 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

4.5.2.1 Step 1: Accessing the MTW Pilot

The user begins by accessing the MTW pilot through the HiDALGO2 Dashboard (Figure 25 left). Selecting the MTW application redirects the user to the MathSO orchestration environment, where workflow management activities are performed. Prior to execution, the user verifies the availability of the required HPC resources and data repositories (Figure 25 right).

Figure 26. (left) Application Page with MTW Filter for Instance Creation; (right) MTW Instance Configuration

4.5.2.2 Step 2: Creating a Simulation Instance

After entering the orchestration environment, the user selects the MTW-Interactive application (Figure 26 left) and creates a new simulation instance. The instance acts as a recipe for all configuration parameters associated with a specific experiment (Figure 26 right). During this stage, the user also selects the desired application binary from the available software repository. A predefined parameter file can be selected from the repository and customized according to the desired experiment. Users may modify physical and numerical parameters such as simulation duration, particle counts, thermal conditions, or other model-specific settings.

Figure 27. Execute Page

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	45 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

4.5.2.3 Step 4: Selecting HPC Resources and Submitting the Simulation

After finalizing the instance configuration, the user proceeds to the execution page (Figure 27). Here, the target HPC system is selected together with the required computational resources. The user specifies the number of compute nodes and parallel tasks required for execution before submitting the simulation to the scheduler.

Figure 28. (left) Execution Graph; (right) Log Inspection

4.5.2.4 Step 5: Monitoring Experiment Execution

Following submission, the experiment becomes visible within the monitoring interface (Figure 27/Figure 29). Users can track the execution status in real time and inspect detailed log files generated during runtime (Figure 28 left). Status information includes scheduler state transitions and execution progress, while log access (Figure 28 right) provides real time insight into software initialization and simulation activity.

Selected	ID	Name	HPC	Status	Created	Finished	Actions
<input type="checkbox"/>	413	Showcase	LUMI-G-unencrypted	failed	2025-09-12 14:59:33	-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	394	MTW-Interactive-MTW-Large-CKAN-Test-2025-9-4_13_47_38	LUMI-G-unencrypted	cancelled	2025-09-04 13:47:40	-	
<input type="checkbox"/>	385	MTW-Interactive-Showcase-MTW-2025-9-4_11_50_10	LUMI-G-unencrypted	completed	2025-09-04 11:50:12	2025-09-04 12:02:47	
<input type="checkbox"/>	377	MTW-Showcase	LUMI-G-unencrypted	completed	2025-09-04 09:13:58	2025-09-04 09:18:42	
<input type="checkbox"/>	369	MTW-Large-Run-MTW-Showcase-2025-9-3_18_23_57	LUMI-G-unencrypted	completed	2025-09-03 18:23:59	2025-09-03 19:08:45	
<input type="checkbox"/>	343	MTW-Large-Run-Production-Data-2025-9-1_10_55_23	LUMI-G-unencrypted	completed	2025-09-01 10:55:26	2025-09-01 11:06:45	
<input type="checkbox"/>	342	MTW-Large-Run-Production-Data-2025-8-25_16_37_41	LUMI-G-unencrypted	completed	2025-08-25 16:37:43	2025-08-25 16:47:02	
<input type="checkbox"/>	341	MTW-Showcase-Choose-Setup-MTW-Result-Type-2025-8-25_16_28_1	LUMI-G-unencrypted	completed	2025-08-25 16:28:03	2025-08-25 16:29:54	
<input type="checkbox"/>	340	MTW-Showcase-Choose-Setup-MTW-Param-File-Small-2025-8-25_16_25_14	LUMI-G-unencrypted	completed	2025-08-25 16:25:16	2025-08-25 16:27:09	
<input type="checkbox"/>	337	MTW-Showcase-MTW-2025-8-25_15_54_42	LUMI-G-unencrypted	completed	2025-08-25 15:54:45	2025-08-25 15:56:37	
<input type="checkbox"/>	323	sing_bin-MPI_CKAN-2025-8-22_15_58_46	LUMI-G-unencrypted	completed	2025-08-22 15:58:48	2025-08-22 16:00:15	
<input type="checkbox"/>	322	sing_bin-MPI_CKAN-2025-8-22_15_57_58	LUMI-G-unencrypted	failed	2025-08-22 15:57:58	-	

Figure 29. Experiments Page

4.5.2.5 Step 7: Retrieving Generated Data

In the final stage, users access the generated datasets through the connected data catalogue. Simulation outputs, archived files, and post-processing products can be downloaded for further analysis. These datasets can subsequently be visualized using external scientific visualization tools such as ParaView.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services			Page:	46 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0
				Status:	Final

5 Feedback, suggestions and additional requirements

As detailed in D2.7, two main campaigns were planned for the collection of the requirements of the Dashboard. Up to the time of this deliverable, the second campaign was completed as well. As there were major updates and features to the service, this second round was also collected from internal partners, including their opinions and requirements. The collection was performed by questionnaire, that was shared among project partners. The following section details the design, creation and management of the questionnaire. Afterwards the results are summarized, compared to the results of the first questionnaire and analyzed.

It is important to note that the Dashboard presented in the current document, as in the previous round, has already been improved according to the feedback provided here. Additionally, the current questionnaire also assesses the quality of pilot integration into the HiDALGO2 ecosystem.

5.1 Questionnaire design

The questionnaire follows the structure of the first questionnaire, with additional questions. It was conducted using google forms. Links to the form were delivered by the HiDALGO2 mailing list to reach all partners. The goal was to have at least one answer from every partner. The questionnaire was still aimed to be short, focusing on five key parts: design, layout, functionalities, usability and responsiveness – as in the first questionnaire – and integration, where partners could rate the quality of pilot integration.

Design still rates style of graphical elements like icons, fonts and pictograms and also style of the visual elements, like boxes. **Layout** rates placement and sizing, including the management of empty space. **Functionalities** rate additional features, like search, filter, tags, sorting and new features like pinning. **Integration** is the new element in this form. Integration support consists of elements and features needed for successfully running pilots within the designated portal.

All key parts were to be rated from 1 to 5, values were defined as in the first questionnaire:

1. It is not acceptable this way, and the following issues need to be addressed as soon as possible.
2. It is acceptable for now, but the following issues need to be addressed in a timely manner.
3. It is OK; however, I do have the following suggestions, which could significantly improve this.
4. It is good; however, I think that it could be improved. – Please give feedback on what you feel that could be improved.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	47 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

- It is perfect as it is, it should not be changed. – Please give feedback on what you liked best.

Participants were required to fill out an additional long format text box for thoughts, opinions and suggestions, one for detailing each valuation. Participants were also asked if there were any services to be added additionally to the Dashboard, if there were any services to be removed or if there are any high level features, that should be included to improve the ecosystem. Participants were also to provide their e-mail address, so that any inconsistencies can be addressed afterwards.

5.2 Questionnaire results

Altogether, 8 answers were submitted. In this section, basic statistics of the answers will be shown, including key responses from long text sections. Eight partners were submitting answers, one answer was submitted per partner. In contrast to the first deliverable, FN did not submit an answer, but ICCS did.

Figure 30. Distribution of questionnaire answers from partners.

For the five major aspects that were analyzed, results are presented as simple pie-charts, showing only number of selections per answer. While all answers will be listed in “Annex I. Second internal feedback on the Dashboard”, some selected feedback will be shown here. While not all reported issues are presented in this section, all issues and opinions will be considered.

Design

The first topic evaluated in the questionnaire was design. Results for the numerical valuation are shown in Figure 31. The overall feedback was strongly positive: most votes were either 5 – perfect or 4 – good, while only one respondent selected 3 – OK. No respondents rated the design as 2 – acceptable or 1 – not acceptable. This indicates that the visual appearance of the current Dashboard release is considered mature and suitable by the internal stakeholders.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	48 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 31. Questionnaire results from internal partners evaluating design

The remarks regarding design were generally positive, with respondents describing the Dashboard as clean, modern, professional, self-explanatory and nice to the eye. The newly introduced Quick Tour feature was also explicitly appreciated, as it helps first-time users understand the Dashboard more easily.

Some recommendations are considered for the next implementation:

- improve the contrast of some text elements in dark mode;
- add separate icon or graphic variants for light and dark themes;
- fix minor visual issues in the Quick Tour, where some buttons do not fully fit into the available space;
- make the visual hierarchy between pilots, workflow orchestrators and other services clearer;
- add a small prefix or icon to widgets such as Portal activity and HPC sites to indicate when the displayed information originates from MathSO.

Some of the most important remarks from other opinions were the following:

- the Dashboard design is considered clean, modern and professional;
- the Dashboard is easy to understand and visually self-explanatory;
- the current design is seen as a good compromise between compactness and clarity;
- the design meets the expected specifications, although further user testing is still needed;
- the Quick Tour feature was welcomed as a useful addition for onboarding new users.

Layout

The second topic evaluated in the questionnaire was layout. Results for the numerical valuation are shown in Figure 32. The overall evaluation was very positive: six respondents rated the layout as 5 – perfect, while two respondents rated it as 4 – good.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	49 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

No respondents selected 3 – OK, 2 – acceptable, or 1 – not acceptable. This indicates that the placement, sizing and general arrangement of the Dashboard elements are considered mature and well suited for the current release.

Figure 32. Questionnaire results from internal partners evaluating layout

The remarks regarding layout were mostly positive. Several respondents highlighted that the Dashboard has a clean and modern structure, with a professional appearance and a compact view that improves the overview of services. The layout was also considered a good compromise between clarity and efficient use of screen space.

Some recommendations are considered for the next implementation:

- fix the reported page-scrolling and mouse-wheel scrolling issues;
- improve behaviour on different screen sizes and browser widths;
- reduce the height of some use-case or pilot cards where possible;
- review the width of the left-side filter panel, as it occupies a significant part of the screen;
- hide the right sidebar when it is not used;
- make the search bar more visible;
- maintain more consistent box sizes when the amount of text differs between cards;
- add more spacing between closely placed elements, especially in the upper-right area of opened pilot cards.

Some of the most important remarks from other opinions were the following:

- the Dashboard layout is considered clean, modern and professional;
- the compact view was explicitly appreciated;
- the overall layout is seen as a good compromise between readability and density;
- the placement of the main Dashboard components is generally clear;

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	50 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

- further testing with end users is still needed to verify that the layout remains intuitive in real use cases;
- improving visual separation between pilots, workflow orchestrators and other services would help users better understand the HiDALGO2 ecosystem.

Functionalities

The third topic evaluated in the questionnaire was functionality. Results for the numerical valuation are shown in Figure 33. The overall feedback was positive: three respondents rated the functionalities as 5 – perfect, while five respondents rated them as 4 – good. No respondents selected 3 – OK, 2 – acceptable, or 1 – not acceptable. This indicates that the currently implemented Dashboard functions are considered useful and mature, while several further improvements were suggested.

Figure 33. Questionnaire results from internal partners evaluating functionalities

The remarks regarding functionality were mostly favourable. Respondents highlighted the usefulness of search, filtering, tagging and navigation functions. The search functionality was explicitly praised as fast and easy to use. Additional positive feedback was received for the HPC Systems tab, including shell access, Jupyter Notebook integration and the querying of available resources on target systems. These features were considered a clear improvement compared to earlier Dashboard versions.

Some recommendations are considered for the next implementation:

- improve the meaning of tags, as partner acronyms alone are not sufficiently informative for external users;
- investigate whether user-defined or functional tags can be added to existing applications;
- reconsider whether all metadata, such as tags and service providers, should be visible on the top level or moved to the details view;
- clarify the purpose of the pinning functionality, or simplify it if it is not needed;
- provide clearer support for defining applications in the Dashboard and cloning them as standalone applications;

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	51 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

- further separate filtering functions from display or view settings, since these currently appear together in the same panel;
- add more advanced HPC-system information queries, for example system information related to GPUs, CPUs or memory, where technically feasible.

Some of the most important remarks from other opinions were the following:

- the Dashboard is easy to understand and provides useful search, filtering, tagging and navigation capabilities;
- searching for tasks was considered particularly fast and efficient;
- the HPC Systems tab, shell integration, Jupyter Notebook integration and resource-querying functions were explicitly appreciated;
- the current functionality already supports daily work better than earlier Dashboard versions;
- not all respondents were able to evaluate editing-related functionality, because not all users had edit access;
- further improvements should focus on clearer tagging, application definition, and more intuitive access to advanced workflow and HPC features.

Usability and responsiveness

The fourth topic evaluated in the questionnaire was usability and responsiveness. Results for the numerical valuation are shown in Figure 34. The overall evaluation was positive: three respondents rated usability and responsiveness as 5 – perfect, three respondents rated it as 4 – good, and two respondents rated it as 3 – OK. No respondents selected 2 – acceptable or 1 – not acceptable. This shows that the Dashboard is generally considered responsive and suitable for daily use, while some usability issues still need to be refined.

Figure 34. Questionnaire results from internal partners evaluating usability and responsiveness

The remarks regarding usability and responsiveness were mostly positive. Respondents highlighted that the Dashboard is fast, responsive and straightforward to

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	52 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

navigate. The improved responsiveness compared to earlier versions was explicitly mentioned, especially from the perspective of pilot development and testing. The portal was also considered useful for modelling, testing pilot integration, rerunning benchmarks and accessing workflow-related functionality.

Some recommendations are considered for the next implementation:

- fix the reported mouse-wheel and page-scrolling issues, as they can prevent users from accessing parts of the content;
- improve the handling of long pages and content-heavy views;
- further improve responsiveness when the browser window width changes;
- test the Dashboard on different screen sizes and common browser configurations;
- add more hints or contextual help to guide users through application and workflow-related functions;
- improve navigation and content accessibility in views where several panels or cards are displayed at the same time.

Some of the most important remarks from other opinions were the following:

- the Dashboard is generally responsive and navigation is straightforward;
- the main actions are easy to find and the layout supports efficient use;
- the responsiveness of the portal has improved significantly compared to earlier versions;
- the Dashboard already supports pilot development and testing activities better than previous releases;
- scrolling behavior remains the most important usability issue to address;
- further refinement is needed to make the portal equally comfortable on different screen sizes and browser layouts.

Integration support

The fifth topic evaluated in the questionnaire was integration support. Results for the numerical valuation are shown in Figure 35. The overall feedback was positive: one respondent rated integration support as 5 – perfect, five respondents rated it as 4 – good, and one respondent rated it as 3 – OK. No respondents selected 2 – acceptable or 1 – not acceptable. This indicates that the Dashboard already provides useful support for pilot integration, while further improvements are still needed to make pilot deployment, workflow configuration and debugging more intuitive.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	53 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Figure 35. Questionnaire results from internal partners evaluating integration support

The remarks regarding integration support were generally positive. Respondents highlighted that the Dashboard provides a useful entry point for pilots and makes it easier to discover, access and present applications within the HiDALGO2 ecosystem. The integration with workflow orchestration was also considered promising, especially where pilots can be modelled as blueprints and executed through the available portal functionality.

Some recommendations are considered for the next implementation:

- provide user guides and tutorials for blueprint designers;
- make the definition of input groups and custom environment variables more visible and intuitive;
- extend the Log Inspector with additional configuration files, such as hpc.cnf, parameters.conf and other relevant input or runtime files;
- consider a debug mode that exports more execution parameters and configuration files to support pilot modelling and troubleshooting;
- add QCG-related widgets similar to the currently available MathSO widgets;
- provide additional flexibility for selecting the simulation environment;
- investigate the possibility of defining workflows by combining different existing applications;
- improve the links between pilots, workflow orchestrators, datasets, documentation and support services.

Some of the most important remarks from other opinions were the following:

- the Dashboard is a useful entry point for pilots and supports their visibility within the HiDALGO2 ecosystem;
- the blueprint-based approach is considered valuable, especially because configuration files can be sourced at execution time;
- further documentation is needed to make pilot modelling easier for new blueprint designers;

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	54 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

- some respondents could not fully evaluate pilot integration because they were not directly involved in a pilot;
- additional widgets for QCG would help provide a more balanced view of the two supported workflow orchestrators;
- future improvements should support more flexible workflow management, including the composition of workflows from existing applications.

Services to be added

Participants were also asked whether additional services should be added to the Dashboard. While several respondents indicated that no further services are currently required, a few specific additions were suggested. These mainly concern pilot-specific interfaces, data-management frontends and additional workflow-related tools.

The most important proposed additions are the following:

- Ktirio.gui was explicitly mentioned as a service to be added. This would provide direct Dashboard access to the graphical interface supporting Ktirio-related scenario preparation, input inspection and visualization.
- HDFS HUE GUI was proposed as a remote frontend for users working with the HiDALGO2 Hadoop-based data-management infrastructure. Since this service requires Kerberos authentication, the Dashboard could provide an external link together with a short information dialog reminding users to authenticate with kinit before accessing the service.
- HDFS and YARN portals were suggested as additional external services for users working with HPDA jobs submitted through Jupyter notebooks. These portals would help users inspect storage status, manage HDFS content and monitor jobs submitted to the Hadoop/YARN infrastructure.
- mUQSA was mentioned as a possible service to consider, although its integration requires further discussion to clarify the intended use case and the appropriate way to expose it through the Dashboard.

Some respondents suggested that additional services should be defined only after a period of use by external users. This indicates that the service catalogue should remain flexible and should be extended based on practical usage patterns and feedback from the wider user community.

Overall, the proposed additions focus on improving access to pilot tools, data-management services and workflow-supporting infrastructure. Since not all respondents requested new services, these additions should be treated as candidate extensions and evaluated according to technical readiness, authentication requirements and relevance for external users.

Services to be removed

Participants were also asked whether any services should be removed from the Dashboard. Compared to the suggestions for adding services, the feedback on

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	55 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

removal was limited. Most respondents indicated that no services should currently be removed, or that they were not sure. This suggests that the current service catalogue is generally considered acceptable by the responding stakeholders.

The most important points regarding service removal are the following:

- **Open Project** was explicitly mentioned as a possible service to remove or reconsider. Its relevance and actual usage within the HiDALGO2 ecosystem should be reviewed.
- Some respondents stated that **no services should be removed**. This indicates that the current Dashboard content is broadly acceptable and that removal should be handled cautiously.
- The **pinning functionality** was questioned by one respondent, but this concerns a Dashboard feature rather than a service.

Overall, the questionnaire does not indicate a strong need to remove services from the Dashboard. The main follow-up action should be to review the role, usage and target audience of Open Project and other potentially overlapping support or collaboration tools, rather than removing them without further validation.

Suggested additional high-level features

Participants were also asked to suggest additional high-level features that could improve the HiDALGO2 Dashboard and services. The answers show that stakeholders are generally satisfied with the current direction of the Dashboard, but several strategic improvements were proposed to make the platform easier to navigate, more informative, and more useful for complex workflow-based use cases.

The most important suggested high-level features are the following:

- Improved navigation and content accessibility were highlighted as important future refinements. Scrolling behavior, long-page handling and access to all visible content should be improved to avoid usability issues.
- Clearer relationships between pilots and services were suggested. The Dashboard should better show which workflow orchestrators, datasets, documentation pages and support services belong to or are relevant for a given pilot.
- Clarification of overlapping service roles was requested. For example, the distinction between community Q&A tools and support/help-desk tools should be made clearer for users.
- Usage statistics or activity indicators were proposed for pilots and services. Such indicators could help users identify active, relevant or recently used resources.
- Extended HPC-system information queries were suggested. In addition to the currently available partition information, users could benefit from system-level information such as GPU, CPU and memory details, where this is technically feasible and does not overload the target systems.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	56 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

- Easier workflow management from existing applications was identified as a possible high-level improvement. Users should be able to define workflows by combining existing applications, for example using the output of one module as the input of another.

Overall, the proposed high-level features point towards a Dashboard that not only lists and launches services, but also explains relationships between them, supports more complex workflows, and provides contextual information about activity, resources and service purpose.

5.3 Results analysis

A summary of the numerical evaluations is shown in Table 4. Overall, the questionnaire results are strongly positive. All currently evaluated areas have an average score of at least **4.00**, and no respondent selected **1 – not acceptable** or **2 – acceptable** in any of the evaluated categories. This indicates that the current release of the Dashboard is considered mature by the responding stakeholders, while still leaving a clear set of improvements for the next implementation cycle.

Compared to the previous questionnaire reported in D2.8, the current results show a clear positive development. The average score increased substantially for **design**, **layout** and **functionality**. Design improved from **3.83** to **4.50**, layout improved from **4.08** to **4.75**, and functionality improved from **3.92** to **4.38**. These improvements suggest that many of the visual, spacing, layout and functional issues identified during the previous feedback round have been successfully addressed in the current release.

Table 4. Distribution and average of questionnaire results compared to previous average.

Aspect	1	2	3	4	5	Average	Previous
Design	0	0	1	2	5	4.50	3.83
Layout	0	0	0	2	6	4.75	4.08
Functionality	0	0	0	5	3	4.38	3.92
Usability & Responsiveness	0	0	2	3	3	4.13	4.25
Integration support	0	0	1	5	1	4.00	-

The current questionnaire also shows that low ratings have disappeared completely. In the previous evaluation, design received two **2 – acceptable** ratings, layout received one **1 – not acceptable** rating, and functionality received several **3 – OK** ratings. In the current results, no category received a **1 – not acceptable** or **2 –**

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	57 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

acceptable rating. This indicates that the Dashboard no longer contains issues that respondents considered critical or only temporarily acceptable.

The strongest improvement can be observed in **design** and **layout**, both increasing by **0.67** points. Respondents described the Dashboard as clean, modern, professional and visually pleasant. The layout was also evaluated very positively, especially the compact view and the improved arrangement of components. This is an important improvement compared to D2.8, where spacing, padding and visual organization were among the most prominent concerns.

Functionality also improved compared to the previous round. Respondents praised the search, filtering, tagging and navigation features. The HPC Systems tab, shell integration, Jupyter Notebook integration and resource-querying functionality were specifically mentioned as important improvements. This shows that the Dashboard has evolved from a service catalogue into a more operational entry point for workflow and HPC-related tasks.

Usability and responsiveness remain positive, but the average score decreased slightly from **4.25** in D2.8 to **4.13** in the current evaluation. This small decrease should not be interpreted as a general regression of the Dashboard, since several respondents explicitly noted that responsiveness is good or has improved compared to earlier versions. Rather, the lower score reflects specific usability issues reported in the current questionnaire, especially scrolling problems, long-page handling and behavior on different screen sizes. These issues should therefore be treated as high-priority refinements for the next implementation cycle.

Integration support was evaluated for the first time in the current questionnaire, so it cannot be directly compared with D2.8. The average score of **4.00** shows that the Dashboard already provides useful support for pilot integration, but that this area is still maturing. Respondents appreciated the Dashboard as an entry point for pilots and as a way to discover, access and present applications within the HiDALGO2 ecosystem. Further improvement is needed for blueprint modelling, documentation for blueprint designers, visibility of custom environment variables and input groups, Log Inspector debugging support, QCG widgets comparable to MathSO widgets, and additional flexibility in selecting the simulation environment.

Regarding services to be added, the most important suggestions were Ktirio.gui, the HDFS HUE GUI, HDFS/YARN portals, and possibly mUQSA after further discussion. Several respondents indicated that additional services should be defined after a period of use by external users. This suggests that the service catalogue should remain flexible and should evolve based on practical user needs, technical readiness and authentication constraints.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	58 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

There was no strong indication that services should be removed from the Dashboard. Most respondents either stated that no services should be removed, were unsure, or left the question unanswered. Open Project was mentioned as a possible service to reconsider, but this should be interpreted as a request to review its relevance and usage, rather than as a direct removal requirement.

The most important high-level improvement proposals point towards a more integrated Dashboard. Respondents suggested clearer links between pilots and the services they use, including workflow orchestrators, datasets, documentation and support channels. They also suggested usage statistics or activity indicators for pilots and services, more advanced HPC-system information queries, and easier workflow management from existing applications. These remarks indicate that future work should focus not only on improving individual Dashboard functions, but also on making relationships between services more visible and actionable.

Based on the results, the following priorities are identified for the next implementation cycle:

- fix scrolling and content-accessibility issues;
- improve responsiveness for different browser widths and screen sizes;
- refine dark-mode contrast and Quick Tour layout;
- improve the visual hierarchy between pilots, workflow orchestrators and support services;
- introduce more meaningful functional tags beyond partner acronyms;
- reconsider which metadata should be shown on the top level, and which should be moved to the details view;
- improve blueprint-designer documentation and debugging support;
- add or evaluate QCG widgets similar to the current MathSO widgets;
- evaluate the integration of Ktirio.gui, HUE, HDFS/YARN portals and mUQSA;
- review Open Project usage before deciding whether it should remain visible as a public Dashboard service;
- explore high-level workflow composition from existing applications.

In conclusion, the current questionnaire confirms that the Dashboard has improved substantially since the feedback round reported in D2.8. The visual design, layout and basic functionality are now considered mature, and the Dashboard is increasingly perceived as an operational tool for pilot and workflow interaction. The remaining requirements are concentrated around usability robustness, clearer service relationships, more meaningful tagging, and deeper pilot/WFO integration.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	59 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

6 Conclusions and Roadmap

6.1 Conclusion

D2.9 reports the current state of the HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services and shows that the Dashboard has matured from a service catalogue into an operational entry point for the HiDALGO2 ecosystem. The current release provides improved layout and design, compact and personalized views, onboarding support, catalogue editing, Keycloak-based access control, and direct links from pilot entries to the MathSO and QCG workflow orchestration environments. The Dashboard now supports not only discovery of services, but also practical access to pilot execution, workflow monitoring and selected portal activity information.

The deliverable also documents the current integration of HiDALGO2 services and pilot applications. Supporting services, development services, workflow orchestrators, data-management components and pilot-specific tools are presented through the Dashboard, while detailed configuration and execution remain delegated to the appropriate specialized systems. This separation is important: the Dashboard provides the common entry point and visibility layer, while workflow execution, HPC access, data management and visualization are handled by the corresponding backend services.

The pilot-integration section demonstrates substantial completeness of the current implementation. UAP, UB, RES, WF and MTW are all represented in the Dashboard and connected to their respective execution environments. The UAP pilot includes several application paths, including RedSIM, Xyst and UAP-FOAM. UB and MTW are integrated through MathSO, while RES and WF use QCG templates. This shows that both supported workflow orchestrators are actively used and that the Dashboard can expose different pilot execution models through a consistent user-facing interface.

The second internal questionnaire confirms the positive development of the Dashboard. Design, layout, functionality, usability and integration support were all evaluated positively, and no category received a critical rating. Compared with the previous feedback round, the most visible improvements are in design, layout and functionality. The remaining issues are therefore not fundamental blockers, but refinements needed to make the system more robust, clearer for external users and easier to use for pilot developers.

Overall, D2.9 shows that the Dashboard and service ecosystem are largely complete for internal operational use and sufficiently mature for controlled external scenarios. The remaining work should focus on targeted usability improvements, clearer service relationships, better support for pilot and blueprint developers, and careful extension of the service catalogue based on realistic user needs.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	60 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

6.2 Roadmap

The roadmap for the next few months focuses on completing and stabilizing the already integrated Dashboard and service functionality, rather than introducing major architectural changes.

The main priorities are:

- **Fix remaining usability issues:** resolve page scrolling and mouse-wheel problems, improve long-page handling, test common browser widths and screen sizes, and correct minor Quick Tour and dark-mode contrast issues.
- **Improve service and pilot presentation:** clarify the visual hierarchy between pilots, workflow orchestrators, data services, documentation and support tools. Review tags so that they describe functions and use cases rather than only partner acronyms.
- **Support pilot and workflow developers:** prepare short guides for blueprint designers, especially for input groups, custom environment variables and workflow configuration. Extend the Log Inspector or add a lightweight debug mode where feasible.
- **Balance MathSO and QCG visibility:** evaluate a first set of QCG-related Dashboard widgets, similar in purpose to the existing MathSO activity and HPC widgets, without duplicating full portal functionality.
- **Review candidate service additions:** evaluate Ktirio GUI, HDFS HUE GUI, HDFS/YARN portals and mUQSA according to technical readiness, authentication requirements and relevance for users. Services requiring special authentication should initially be exposed only as clearly marked external links with short usage instructions.
- **Prepare controlled external access:** keep external users under HiDALGO2 Keycloak, with approval by both the pilot responsible or service provider and a HiDALGO2 administrator. Institution-wide access for external organizations should not be introduced at this stage.
- **Treat advanced features as exploratory:** workflow composition from existing applications, richer usage statistics and extended HPC system-information queries should be limited to feasibility checks or small prototypes during the next period.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	61 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

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Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	62 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Annexes

Annex I. Internal feedback on the Dashboard

Questionnaire

Guidelines

Second internal feedback from HiDALGO2 partners is on the current implementation of the HiDALGO2 Ecosystem, which consists of all services provided by the HiDALGO2 consortium.

Please, take your time to read carefully. The questionnaire is short.

We would like to have short feedback on the topic. Please rate design, layout, functionalities and responsiveness and also integration. Please give feedback on every point, sharing your suggestions, opinions, if you have found any issues, or if you find something particularly positive. Also, please indicate if any additional services need to be integrated into or removed from the dashboard.

Please consider the full path of your pilot execution, including parts within the MathSO/QCG portal side.

Ratings will go from 1 to 5, with the numbers having the following meaning:

5: It is perfect as it is, it should not be changed.

- Please give feedback on what you liked best.

4: It is good; however, I think that it could be improved.

- Please give feedback on what you feel could be improved.

3: It is OK; however, I do have the following suggestions, which could significantly improve this.

2: It is acceptable for now, but the following issues need to be addressed in a timely manner.

1: It is not acceptable this way, and the following issues need to be addressed as soon as possible.

Independent from the rating, please share your insights, suggestions, and any issues you have found.

Please, also provide your e-mail, so we can contact you later, if any clarification is needed.

Questions

- Please rate the design of the dashboard. Design consists of graphical elements, like icons, fonts, pictograms, style of visual elements, like boxes.
- Please share your thoughts, opinions and suggestions for design.
- Please rate the layout of the dashboard. Layout consists of the placement and sizing of the various elements, including management of empty space.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	63 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

- Please share your thoughts, opinions and suggestions for layout.
- Please rate the functionalities of the dashboard. Functionalities include the ability to search and filter tiles, the support for a detail page, tags and sorting. Later functionalities will include user roles and editing. Whoever has access to editing, please also include its rating here.
- Please share your thoughts, opinions and suggestions for functionalities.
- Please rate the usability and responsiveness of the dashboard. Usability means that its functionalities efficiently support daily work and activities. Responsiveness refers to the speed of the portal.
- Please share your thoughts, opinions and suggestions for usability and responsiveness.
- Please rate the integration support of your pilot of the dashboard. Integration support consists of elements and features needed for successfully running your pilot within the designated portal.
- Please share your thoughts, opinions and suggestions for integration support of your pilot.
- Please indicate if there are any additional services to be added to the dashboard.
- Please indicate if there are any additional services to be removed from the dashboard.
- What additional high-level features do you suggest to improve the HiDALGO2 dashboard and services?

Answers

Please rate the **design** of the dashboard. Design consists of graphical elements, like icons, fonts, pictograms, style of visual elements, like boxes.

3 - OK

5 - perfect

5 - perfect

4 - good

4 - good

5 - perfect

5 - perfect

5 - perfect

Please share your thoughts, opinions and suggestions for design.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	64 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

nice design, but some vexing behavior (eg scrolling does not work well)

I feel it was very good, and happy to see the new Quick Tour feature when you first go the dashboard.

I like that it is very clean, nice to the eye, and self-explanatory.

The design meets the specifications, but we haven't been able to test it yet to make sure it's easy for users to use and understand.Both MatSho and QCG.

In general the design is OK, however there a few improvements that may be considered:

1. Currently, the role of filter panel is twofold. It defines filtering (which is natural) and the display settings (which adds an additional dimension and may be misleading). I think that it would be better to separate these two sets of components in GUI.
2. The dark mode is fine, however there should be an option to enable two flavors of graphics / icons: one for the light theme and one for the dark theme.
3. I see that there are already nice widgets for the Portal activity and HPC sites, which is OK, but I would suggest to add some prefix / icon that will indicate that this information comes from MathSO.

I've just noticed some buttons (e.g. next) don't fit into the Guide Tour

N/A

The design is an excellent compromise.

Please rate the layout of the dashboard. Layout consists of the placement and sizing of the various elements, including management of empty space.

4 - good

5 - perfect

5 - perfect

5 - perfect

4 - good

5 - perfect

5 - perfect

5 - perfect

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	65 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

Please share your thoughts, opinions and suggestions for layout.

page scrolling does not work : NO GO !
 dark mode is attractive but some text appears relatively small and low contrast.
 Card height is large: Each use-case card occupies a significant amount of vertical space.

The left panel consumes approximately 15–20% of the screen width.
 right sidebar should be hidden if not used
 The search bar is somewhat hidden.
 clearly distinguish visual hierarchy between pilot, workflow, ... This would help users understand immediately the ecosystem, I believe

I think it is very good.

No comments. It just looks like a clean modern website.

The design meets the specifications, but we haven't been able to test it yet to make sure it's easy for users to use and understand

The overall layout looks correct, but in some places the boxes sizes aren't maintained when the amount of text varies. Also in some places it would be nice to add a bit more space between components. E.g. in the right top corner of the pilot boxes, when a given pilot was opened, there is a bit too less space between buttons and the text "Opened Xm ago"

I am impressed with the new Dashboard layout and visual design. Very professional

I really like the compact view

The layout is an excellent compromise, too.

Please rate the functionalities of the dashboard. Functionalities include the ability to search and filter tiles, the support for a detail page, tags and sorting. Later functionalities will include user roles and editing. Who have access to editing, please also include its rating here.

4 - good

4 - good

5 - perfect

4 - good

4 - good

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	66 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

5 - perfect

5 - perfect

4 - good

Please share your thoughts, opinions and suggestions for functionalities.

The dashboard is easy to understand and provides useful search, filtering, tagging, and navigation capabilities. The overall design is modern and professional. The main issue I encountered is that scrolling does not work correctly, which prevents access to part of the content. Fixing this would significantly improve usability. Additional filtering, sorting, and personalization features could further enhance the user experience.

I do not have edit access, so not sure.

I'm really impressed with how well searching for tasks works. It is fast and easy to use. I'm also a big fan of all functionalities within the HPC Systems tab. The shell and Jupyter Notebook integration work seamlessly and look nice. Querying the available resources of a target system is also quick and nicely presented, way nicer than using sinfo in the terminal. I'm impressed by the progress of MathSO since the last questionnaire. Impressive work.

The design meets the specifications, but we haven't been able to test it yet to make sure it's easy for users to use and understand.

I am not sure whether there is a need to display all "metadata" information on the top level. E.g. is this interesting for a final user what are the tags associated with a given pilot, or who is a service provider? Maybe it should be hidden in details so as not to distract the user on a high level?

I wonder why the only available tags are partner acronyms. They are meaningless for external users, and only serve for selecting apps by partner owner. Could be possible to add new tags (by user) so the user can tag existing applications by applying these new tags?

N/A

Needed: definition of the application in the dashboard and then clone it as a standalone app.

Please rate the usability and responsiveness of the dashboard. Usability means, that its functionalities efficiently support daily work and activities. Responsiveness refers to the speed of the portal.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	67 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

3 - OK

4 - good

5 - perfect

4 - good

3 - OK

5 - perfect

5 - perfect

4 - good

Please share your thoughts, opinions and suggestions for usability and responsiveness.

The portal is generally responsive and navigation is straightforward. The layout is clear and the main actions are easy to find. However, usability is currently affected by scrolling issues that make some content difficult or impossible to access. Improving navigation, handling of long pages, and support for different screen sizes would significantly enhance the user experience. Overall, responsiveness is good, but usability still needs refinement.

The scroll through my mouse scroll wheel was not working.

Compared to the version from December 2025, the responsiveness of the portal has increased immeasurably, which makes modeling and testing the pilot integration into the dashboard way easier for me as a developer. Regarding the usability of the dashboard from a user perspective, I cannot say much since I'm developing the pilot application and mainly apply and test changes to the pilot framework that would require an adjustment of the blueprint, which makes working directly on the target and test systems more reasonable for me. But I see advantages in rerunning benchmarks and tests using the orchestrator.

The design meets the specifications, but we haven't been able to test it yet to make sure it's easy for users to use and understand.

I think that the responsiveness should be improved: the change of the width of the browser causes significant problems in a proper placement of components etc.

Dashboard is quite responsive up to what I am able to test

N/A

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	68 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

More "hints" would be great to ease the application.

Please rate the integration support of your pilot of the dashboard. Integration support consists of elements and features needed for successfully running your pilot within the designated portal.

4 - good

3 - OK

4 - good

4 - good

4 - good

4 - good

5 - perfect

Please share your thoughts, opinions and suggestions for integration support of your pilot.

The dashboard provides a useful entry point for our pilot and makes it easier to discover, access, and present the application within the Hidalgo2 ecosystem.

The way to model the pilot as a blueprint within the orchestrator was not really intuitive to me. Especially the custom environment variables that define an input group are a bit hidden. A user's guide and tutorials for blueprint designers would be helpful.

I really like the concept of defining everything as a config file and sourcing it at execution time.

I would love to have all the MathSO config files `hpc.cnf`, `parameters.conf`, other(?) in the Log Inspector as well, or at least some kind of debug mode that exports more parameters input files into this very convenient view to ease debugging the modeling of pilots / applications / blueprints into the orchestrator.

The design meets the specifications, but we haven't been able to test it yet to make sure it's easy for users to use and understand.

In the future It would be good to add similar widgets for QCG as those for MathSO

I am not able to evaluate this as I am not involved in any pilot

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	69 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

N/A
Maybe to define workflows from different applications.
Please indicate, if there are any additional services to be added to the dashboard.
Ktirio.gui
Not sure.
I'm happy with how it is right now.
Once the integration is complete in this first phase, we will consider the possibility of adding some additional flexibility to the selection of the simulation environment.
Maybe we could think about adding mUQSA (needs discussion in what way).
I think the HDFS HUE GUI could be integrated as a remote frontend (external link), although it requires to user to log into Kerberos using kinit in a console window. Possibly the Dashboard could show a message dialog to the user reminding him to do so when clicking on the Dashboard icon for the HUE GUI. Similarly, the HDSF/YARN portal could be integrated as an external service for users sending HPDA jobs to this infrastructure using the Jupyter notebooks. Contact me for connection links.
N/A
Additional services should be defined after a period of use by external users.
Please indicate, if there are any additional services to be removed from the dashboard.
Open Project and probably others !
I am not sure if the pinning functionality for each card is needed.
I'm happy with how it is right now.
There is not.
No one
N/A
none

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	70 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final

What additional high level features do you suggest to improve the HiDALGO2 dashboard and services?

Improve navigation and usability, particularly scrolling and content accessibility. Clarify the distinction between some services whose purposes may overlap from a user perspective (e.g., community Q&A versus support/help desk). Provide clearer links between pilots and the services they use (workflows, datasets, documentation, support). Finally, adding brief usage statistics or activity indicators for pilots and services would help users identify the most active and relevant resources.

Not sure.

If possible, I would like to have a query in "HPC Systems" similar to the "View Partitions" but for system information. E.g., output from ``nvidia-smi``, ``lscpu``, ``lshw``, ``cat /proc/cpuinfo``, ``cat /proc/meminfo`` including ``grep`` features that support an easy grap with regex expressions. But for the partitions, not for the login node. I'm not sure if this is possible. It would probably require storing these outputs since allocating a job for this every time seems rather problematic.

No one else excepting those I mentioned in my previous comment

N/A

Easy-to-use workflow management from the existing apps. E.g. if we had a WRF module running from the portal, and another app W-app that needs weather data, then to be able to define a workflow that is built from WRF and W-app.

Document name:	D2.9 HiDALGO2 Dashboard and Services				Page:	71 of 71
Reference:	D2.9	Dissemination:	PU	Version:	1.0	Status: Final